

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ROIT****FIRST NAME: NATASHA****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 8%

The author used the following software: Microsoft 365 on Windows 11

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What are the three categories of citations?

- short-form, long-form, and references
- in-text, footnotes, and bibliography¹**
- short form, footnotes, and bibliography
- in-text, long-form, and bibliography

2. What are the two categories of online sources?

- (1) distinguished only by the use of the online medium and (2) unique to the online medium²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (4th ed., Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 35-39.

² Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, revised Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff, 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 143.

- (1) available online through paid access only and (2) available online free to the public
- (1) accessible only through the use of Zotero and (2) available online through paid access only
- (1) distinguished only by the use of the online medium and (2) accessible only through the use of Zotero

3. What is the difference between *practical* and *conceptual* research problems?

- Practical research problems encompass situations to be addressed, with the consequences exhibiting a tangible effect. Conceptual research problems address knowledge with the goal of better understanding.³**
- Practical research problems address what is practically possible. Conceptual research problems address what is intellectually understandable.
- Practical research problems are for daily applications. Conceptual research problems are for theoretical applications.
- Practical research problems address the best methods to accomplish technical innovations. Conceptual research problems address research for which grants are available.

³ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertation*, 29.

4. Which of the following best describes the difference between *applied* and *pure* research?
- “What we should think” for applied research and “what we should do” for pure research.
 - “How to apply citations to the thesis” for applied research and “how to hypothesize” for pure research.
 - “How to apply for research grants” for applied research and “how to write academic papers pure of thought” for pure research.
 - “What we should do” for applied research and “what we should think” for pure research.⁴**
5. Which of the choices below best defines primary, secondary, and tertiary sources.
- Primary sources are original materials containing raw data or evidence. Secondary sources are particular field’s literature. Tertiary sources are generally books and articles synthesizing secondary sources.⁵**
 - Primary sources are those used primarily in academic writing. Secondary sources are to be used only if primary sources have been exhausted. Tertiary sources should never be used.
 - Primary sources are original materials containing raw data or evidence. Secondary sources are non-peer-reviewed sources. Tertiary sources should never be used.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ Ibid., 37.

- Primary sources are original materials containing raw data or evidence. Secondary sources are particular field's literature. Tertiary sources refer to the Tertiary period.
6. What three schemata categories are advocated by Sampson for use in dissertations?
- (1) specialization (concepts divided into component parts), (2) substantive (describing the end result of the research), and (3) theoretical (used to develop multiple hypotheses)
- (1) specialization (concepts divided into component parts), (2) generalization (concrete concepts integrated into more abstract concepts), and (3) procedural (used to understand the sequence needed to complete a complex task)⁶**
- (1) generalization (concrete concepts integrated into more abstract concepts), (2) substantive (describing the end result of the research), and (3) theoretical (used to develop multiple hypotheses)
- (1) specialization (concepts divided into component parts), (2) theoretical (used to develop multiple hypotheses), and (3) procedural (used to understand the sequence needed to complete a complex task).

⁶ James Sampson, Jr., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University 2017), 16-17.

7. What is the purpose of the dissertation's Method Chapter?
- to describe the student's method for using citations
 - to convey the student's method of developing the hypothesis
 - to convey the student's methodology and philosophy in conducting the dissertation research⁷**
 - to invite the reader to contribute to the future methods for the dissertation's particular topic
8. What is the difference between qualitative and quantitative research?
- Qualitative research refers to utilizing fewer materials of higher quality. Quantitative research refers to utilizing a large quantity of materials irrespective of quality.
 - Qualitative research utilizes descriptive data to gain an understanding of social reality. Quantitative research employs mathematical models and theories such as statistics and percentages.⁸**
 - Qualitative research uses descriptive data to gain an understanding of social reality. Quantitative research is the same as qualitative research but uses more data.
 - Qualitative research refers to utilizing fewer materials of higher quality than quantitative research.

⁷ Ibid., 34.

⁸ Philip Adu, *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study*. National Center for Academic and Dissertation Excellence (YouTube, 2016), 0:35 min.

9. Which of the following most accurately describes the two elements of data analysis: congruence and accuracy?

- Congruence requires agreement between the hypotheses and the preceding literature. Accuracy means providing evidence that the writer's analytical techniques support the hypothesis.
- Congruence requires a rationale for how the data analysis method fits the framed hypotheses. Accuracy refers to the correctness of citations.
- Congruence means compatibility between in-text and bibliography citations. Accuracy refers to the accuracy of the citations.
- Congruence requires a rationale for how the data analysis method fits the framed hypothesis. Accuracy means providing evidence that the writer's analytical techniques support the hypothesis.⁹**

10. What is the difference between “delimitations” and “limitations” in dissertation writing?

- Delimitations are anticipated boundaries for the dissertation research methods set by the researcher, while limitations are unanticipated problems.¹⁰**
- Delimitations are boundaries set by the researcher, while limitations are boundaries set by peer review committees.
- Delimitations are unexpected research problems, while limitations are anticipated boundaries set by the researcher.

⁹ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 47.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 49, 59.

- Delimitations are boundaries set by the university, while limitations are boundaries set by the researcher.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.